

EXPLORING INTERNATIONAL PRACTICES IN THE FIELD OF GREEN CODING

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Abstract

Green coding is a relatively recent term used to refer to programming code that is produced and written in a way that minimizes the software's energy consumption, thereby limiting its potential impact on the environment. This paper explores international practice of green coding for software. Six popular practices are studied out of them. Practices for sustainable software development on green coding are analyzed and recommendations are given in this area. Simple ways to write less malicious code into the environment are shown. These simple techniques will help create software code that puts less pressure on computers and servers.

Keywords: Green code, program, energy, green computing, experience, utility

INTRODUCTION

Green coding is a software engineering term that describes a set of methods used to create applications that consume as little energy as possible.

Green coding is a relatively recent term used to refer to programming code that is produced and written in a way that minimizes the software's energy consumption, thereby limiting its potential impact on the environment.

Green coding principles should not be considered contrary to existing practices. Rather, they should be incorporated into software engineers' principles to consider when writing and designing code to balance functionality and power consumption [1].

The telecommunications and ICT industry is a major contributor to carbon emissions on a global scale. These emissions come from a variety of sources, including the energy required to power telecommunications companies' cellular networks, the manufacturing and distribution of phones, and emissions associated with the processing of other digital applications and technologies. These emissions will continue to increase as the use of digital technologies rises.

RELATED WORK

1. In the present scenario green computing is not only ethical and obligatory but it is a profitable, feasible and ultimate solution. There is a strong need for a mega-trend in the future to save the environment because the rate at which the oil, gases, fauna are being used for power generation, and the rate at which the environment is getting polluted by industries, domestic waste, vehicles constitute a Himalayan threat to the health of human beings. The power consumption is increasing enormously due to the use of ICT infrastructure in the world and hence it is increasing the carbon footprint every day. So therefore we have to reduce the consumption of energy and natural resources which is used by ICT. Efforts have been made to reduce the consumption of power in H/W design which is the Green IT. But there is a lack of models, descriptions, or realizations in the field of computer software although it is necessary for successful implementation of Green Computing. Moreover there are hardly any systematic algorithms available that try to integrate sustainability

aspects in software product design and development. Till now it is not clear what the term sustainable software means or what would be criterion for a sustainable software. The software development process models do not address or emphasize on sustainability and greener aspects of software and the development process. In the present work the authors have made an effort to understand the sustainability aspects of software and try to suggest some improvements in the SDLC models to include the greener aspects of software development [2].

2. Thus, we need to reduce software energy consumption while maintaining the same functionalities for the software in order to build sustainable and green software. Firstly, in this thesis work, we define the terms sustainable and green in the area of software development. To build a software product, we need to follow a software engineering process. Hence, we define and describe sustainable and green criteria to be respected after each step of this process in order to establish a sustainable and green software engineering process. Then, we focus on the software energy consumption estimation. Many research works tried to propose various tools to estimate the energy consumption due to software in order to reduce carbon footprint [3].

3. The energy efficiency of IT has become one of the hottest topics in the last few years. The problem has been typically addressed by hardware manufacturers and designers, but recently the attention of industry and academia has shifted to the role of software for IT sustainability. Writing energy-efficient software is one of the most challenging issues in this area, because it requires not only a change of mindset for software developers and designers but also models and tools to measure and reduce the effect of software on the energy consumption of the underlying hardware. In this article, the authors present a conceptual framework that provides a unifying view of the strategies, models, and tools available so far for designing and developing greener software [4].

4. Information Communication Technology (ICT) has a strong impact on sustainable development due its rising demands for energy and resources needed when building hardware and software products. Most of the efforts spent on Green ICT/IT have been dedicated to addressing the effects of hardware on the environment

but little have been considering the effects of building software products as well. Efficient software will indirectly consume less energy by using up less hardware equipment to run. Our contributions in this paper are devoted to building a two level green software model that covers the sustainable life cycle of a software product and the software tools promoting green and environmentally sustainable software. In the first level we propose a new green software engineering process that is a hybrid process between sequential, iterative, and agile development processes to produce an environmentally sustainable one. Each stage of the software process is then further studied to produce a green and sustainable stage. We propose either green guidelines or green processes for each software stage in the engineering process. We add to the software life cycle the requirements stage and the testing stage. We also include in the first level a complete list of metrics to measure the greenness of each stage in terms of the first order effects of ICT on the environment for a green

software engineering process. No effort has been placed before in designing a green software engineering process. The second level explains how software itself can be used as a tool to aid in green computing by monitoring resources in an energy efficient manner. Finally, we show and explain relationships that can be found between the two levels in our proposed model to make the software engineering process and product green and sustainable [5].

GREEN CODING: 6 PRACTICES FOR SUSTAINABLE SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT

While researching the international experience in the field of green coding, 6 important practices have attracted attention among the practices available for the development of a sustainable software system. Green coding helps create programs that are less harmful to the environment and run more efficiently. Here are the top 6 ways to write green code (fig.1) [6]:

Fig. 1. 6 best ways to write green code

By applying these methods, it is possible to create a software system that is less harmful to the environment and works more efficiently.

Table 1 at various stages of software development, it has a negative impact on the environment:

Stage	Impact on nature
Extraction of materials	Damage in the extraction of meals and rare elements
Production	Contamination of servers and device during production
Usage	High energy consumption data centers
Utilization	Challenges in e-waste recycling

Table 2, They reduce the number of calculations and the load on the computer. For example:

Type of algorithm	Impact on energy consumption
Simple	More calculations, more consumption
Optimal	Less computing, less consumption

2. Saving resources

Less resources = less energy. How to do it:

- Effective data storage;
- Reducing network traffic;
- Using virtualization.

3. Choosing green hosting

Green hosting runs on clean energy. This reduces the environmental impact of applications. Cloud technologies also help to save energy.

4. Improving development methods

Correct design methods reduce waste and energy consumption [6]:

- Benefits of the proposed method;
- Continuous integration;
- Fewer errors and program restarts;
- Code reuse;
- Simple design of the module;
- Facilitation of updating parts of the program;
- And so on.

5. Writing energy saving code

- Energy should be considered when writing code;
- Measuring the program's energy consumption;

▪ Finding a balance between speed and energy saving;

- Choosing programming languages that consume less energy (Cu, C#, C+, etc.)

6. Planning long-term use

A program that runs for a long time without being replaced is less harmful to the environment. How to achieve this:

- Advance planning of updates;
- Careful management of digital resources;
- Modular design for easy replacement of parts.

How to start green coding? Green coding helps create applications that are less harmful to the environment. Here's how to get started with green coding:

- Goal setting;
- Making decisions to achieve the goal;
- Reducing 20% of energy consumption;
- Reducing 30% of waste;
- Checking current affairs;
- Determining how much energy it consumes;
- Determining what resources to use;
- Determining how much waste is generated;
- Selection of the necessary tools.

Table 3. New technologies in green coding

Technology	How it helps
Information technologies	Creation of effective algorithms
Platform to check	Measuring the impact of programs on nature
New standards	Determining the rules of green development
Education	Teaching how to write "green" code

CONCLUSION

Green coding helps reduce the impact of applications on the environment and makes them better. Even small changes at work can make a big difference to the environment. Writing green code and applying these techniques to work can be still explored. Below are some simple ways to write less malicious software code for the environment, and following these tips can get good results: Using a good algorithm; Not writing additional code; Saving memory; Selecting energy-saving programming languages; Optimization of work with databases; Using caching; And forth. These simple techniques will help create applications that put less efforts on computers and servers. The 29th session of the Conference of the Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (COP29) to be held on November 11-22, 2024 in Baku, Azerbaijan will also contribute to green coding [7].

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